

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
1	ABB Limited Process Automation Stonehouse, UK	https://global.abb/	AK 100 Series
2	ABB Limited Process Automation Stonehouse, UK	https://global.abb/	EL3000 Series
3	ABB Limited Process Automation Stonehouse, UK	https://global.abb/	EL3060 Series
4	AirTest Technologies Corp.Delta, Canada	https://www.airtest.com/product/index.html	TR5200 CG
6	Alphasense Ltd. Great Notley, UK	https://www.alphasense.com/products/	H2 AF
7	Alphasense Ltd. Great Notley, UK	https://www.alphasense.com/products/	CH-A3

U	Acc date	Technology
U(2)	17.10.2013	Thermal conductivity Katharometer
U(1)	01.11.2013	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	01.11.2013	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	08.11.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	27.09.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	24.10.2013	Catalytic Pellistor

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Hydrogen purity and purge gas monitor ATEX compliant gas analyser system.	Hydrogen purity analysis: 85 to 100% H2 80 to 100% H2 user selectable Purge gas analysis: 0 to 100% hydrogen in purge gas 0 to 100% air in purge gas	
Continuous gas analysis, measurement of H2 in air and various gases and also various gases in H2	Smallest Measurement Ranges: 0 - 11 vol.% H2 in air, Ar, CH4, CO CO2, N2 0 - 10 vol.% H2 in NH3 0 - 13 vol.% air, Ar, CO, CO2, N2 in H2 0 - 14 vol.% CH4 in H2 0-10 vol.% NH3 in H2	
Continuous gas analysis, measurement of H2 in air and various gases and also various gases in H2; Special version for monitoring hydrogen-cooled turbo generators	Smallest Measurement Ranges: 0 - 1 vol.% H2 in air, Ar, CH4, CO CO2, N2 0 - 10 vol.% H2 in NH3 0 - 3 vol.% air, Ar, CH4, CO, CO2, N2 in H2 0 - 14 vol.% CH4 in H2 0-10 vol.% NH3 in H2 Special Version: 100 - 0 vol.% H2 in CO2 100 - 80/90 vol.% H2 in air	
Battery charging rooms, vehicle maintenance facilities, hydrogen gas fueling facilities, below ground facilities, etc.	Standard Range: 0 - 100% LEL Combustible Gas Minimum Detectable: 2% LEL	
Emissions monitoring, process safety, environmental monitoring, volatile organic compounds (VOCs)	Limit of performance warranty: 2000 ppm	
fixed or portable application	0 - 100% LEL methane	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
8	Alphasense Ltd. Great Notley, UK	https://www.alphasense.com/products/	CH-D3
9	Analogx Stokesley, UK	https://www.analogxgroup.com/?industrial-safety.php	3003 SI
10	Applied Nanotech Inc. Austin, TX, USA	http://www.appliednanotech.net/tech/mnps.php	MNPS-B
11	Sciosense B.V. High Tech Campus 10 5656 AE Eindhoven The Netherlands (AppliedSensor GmbH Reutlingen, Germany)	https://www.sciosense.com/	HLS-440
12	Sciosense B.V. High Tech Campus 10 5656 AE Eindhoven The Netherlands (AppliedSensor GmbH Reutlingen, Germany)	https://www.sciosense.com/	HLS-440P
13	Sciosense B.V. High Tech Campus 10 5656 AE Eindhoven The Netherlands (AppliedSensor GmbH Reutlingen, Germany)	https://www.sciosense.com/	HPS-100

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	24.10.2013	Catalytic Pellistor
U(1)	08.11.2013	Electrochemical Galvanic Fuel Cell
U(1)	17.10.2013	Other/ New Nanotechnology /Resistive
U(1)	23.10.2013	Combination of Work function Field effect transistor & Thermal conductivity
U(1)	23.10.2013	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	23.10.2013	Thermal conductivity

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
portable application	0 - 100% LEL methane	
Industrial Safety	0 - 1000 ppm 0 - 2000 ppm	
Fuel cells, hydrogen storage, automotive, back-up power systems, portable gas detectors and monitors, power transformers	0 - 10000 ppm Lowest detection limit: 10 ppm	
Hydrogen gas leak detection in hydrogen- powered vehicles (sensor locations at cabin ceiling, under the hood of the engine compartment, beneath the trunk lid);leak detection at hydrogen fueling stations	0 - 4.4% H2 in air	
Hydrogen gas leak detection in fuel cell systems(e.g. exhausts) and other in-process application	0 - 10% H2 in air or N2	
Hydrogen gas measurement in fuel cell systems(e.g. exhausts) and other in-process application	0 - 100% H2 in N2	

Type
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
14	Arrgh!! Manufacturing Co. Inc. Novato, CA, USA	https://www.arrgh.com/	H2 - Hydrogen Gas Detector
15	Asensor Technologies Co. Ltd. Shenzhen, China	http://www.szasensor.com/	DH4-H2-500
16	Asensor Technologies Co. Ltd. Shenzhen, China	http://www.szasensor.com/	DH4-H2-1000
17	Asensor Technologies Co. Ltd. Shenzhen, China	http://www.szasensor.com/	DH4-H2-10000
18	Asensor Technologies Co. Ltd. Shenzhen, China	http://www.szasensor.com/	DH7-H2-500
19	Asensor Technologies Co. Ltd. Shenzhen, China	http://www.szasensor.com/	DH7-H2-1000

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	08.11.2013	Resistive Semiconductor
U(1)	06.11.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	06.11.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	06.11.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	06.11.2013	Electrochemical Amperometric
U(1)	06.11.2013	Electrochemical Amperometric

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Lead-acid battery charging rooms and other areas	n/a	
Hydrogen gas detection and monitoring for Industrial Safety, Mining, Residential Safety, Emissions, Environmental Monitoring	0 - 500 ppm	
Hydrogen gas detection and monitoring for Industrial Safety, Mining, Residential Safety, Emissions, Environmental Monitoring	0 - 1000 ppm	
Hydrogen gas detection and monitoring for Industrial Safety, Mining, Residential Safety, Emissions, Environmental Monitoring	0 - 10000 ppm	
Hydrogen gas detection and monitoring for Industrial Safety, Mining, Residential Safety, Emissions, Environmental Monitoring	0 - 500 ppm	
Hydrogen gas detection and monitoring for Industrial Safety, Mining, Residential Safety, Emissions, Environmental Monitoring	0 - 1000 ppm	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
20	Asensor Technologies Co. Ltd.Shenzhen, China	http://www.szasensor.com/	DH7-H2-10000
21	Asensor Technologies Co. Ltd.Shenzhen, China	http://www.szasensor.com/	KG100A
22	Asensor Technologies Co. Ltd.Shenzhen, China	http://www.szasensor.com/	KG100B
23	Asensor Technologies Co. Ltd.Shenzhen, China	http://www.szasensor.com/	KG2100A
24	Asensor Technologies Co. Ltd.Shenzhen, China	http://www.szasensor.com/	KG2100B
25	AST American Sensor Technologies Inc. Mount Olive,NJ, USA	https://www.te.com/usa-en/products/brands/ast.html?tab=pgp-story	AST 2000 H2

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	06.11.2013	Electrochemical Amperometric
U(1)	05.11.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	24.10.2013	Mechanical Piezoresistive

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Hydrogen gas detection and monitoring for Industrial Safety, Mining, Residential Safety, Emissions, Environmental Monitoring	0 - 10000 ppm	
Monitoring of the concentration of a specific gas in a target environment Application fields: energy, electric power, petrochemical, nuclear power, etc.	0 - 5000 µL/L	
Monitoring of the concentration of a specific gas in a target environment Application fields: energy, electric power, petrochemical, nuclear power, etc.	0 - 5000 µL/L	
Determination of gases in different fields, e.g. electric power, nuclear power, etc.	0 - 5000 µL/L	
Determination of gases in different fields, e.g. electric power, nuclear power, etc.	0 - 5000 µL/L	
PEM fuel cells, hydrogen storage, hydrogen filling stations, back-up power, test stands, e.g. control of hydrogen flow to fuel cell stack.	Available Pressure Ranges: 20 bar, 448 bar, 500 bar, 700 bar, 900 bar	Pressure sensor

Type
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen detection apparatus
n/a

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
26	AST American Sensor Technologies Inc. Mount Olive,NJ, USA	https://www.te.com/usa-en/products/brands/ast.html?tab=pgp-story	AST 4000
27	AST American Sensor Technologies Inc. Mount Olive,NJ, USA	https://www.te.com/usa-en/products/brands/ast.html?tab=pgp-story	AST 4300
29	AST American Sensor Technologies Inc. Mount Olive,NJ, USA	https://www.te.com/usa-en/products/brands/ast.html?tab=pgp-story	AST 4600
30	Bacharach Inc. New Kensington, PA, USA	https://www.mybacharach.com/	Leakator® 10
31	BERNT Messtechnik Düsseldorf, Germany	https://www.bernt-messtechnik.de/	GP2000HL
32	Bieler + Lang GmbH Achern,Germany	https://bieler-lang.de/?id=5&amp%3BL=1	Exmonitor / Gasmonitor H2 1000

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	24.10.2013	Mechanical Piezoresistive
U(1)	24.10.2013	Mechanical Piezoresistive
U(1)	24.10.2013	Mechanical Piezoresistive
U(1)	08.11.2013	(Solid state / Semiconductor; patented)
U(1)	01.11.2013	(Semiconductor) Electrochemical
U(1)	05.12.2013	Electrochemical

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
PEM Fuel Cells, Hydrogen Filling Stations, Back Up Power, Hydrogen Storage, etc. Used, for instance, at outlet valve of fuel storage vessels	All pressures between 0 - 25 PSI and 0 - 10000 PSI	Pressure sensor
Hydrogen fuel, gas compression and storage	All pressures between 0 - 25 PSI and 0 - 10000 PSI	Pressure sensor
Industrial OEM & Hydrogen Equipment	0 - 20000 PSI	Pressure sensor
Leak detection	20 ppm Sensitivity, methane-based	
Monitoring of areas with restricted or no accessibility, gas withdrawal from machines and exhaust pipes	min. 0 - 100 ppm max. 0 - 2000 ppm	
Industrial safety equipment, monitoring of gas concentration and warning	0 - 1000 ppm (standard range; 0 - 2000 ppm available)	

Type
n/a
n/a
n/a
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
33	Bieler + Lang GmbH Achern,Germany	https://bieler-lang.de/?id=5&amp%3BL=1	ExDetector HC- 100
34	Bieler + Lang GmbH Achern,Germany	https://bieler-lang.de/?id=5&amp%3BL=1	ExDetector HC- 150
35	Bieler + Lang GmbH Achern,Germany	https://bieler-lang.de/?id=5&amp%3BL=1	ExDetector HC- 200
36	Bieler + Lang GmbH Achern,Germany	https://bieler-lang.de/?id=5&amp%3BL=1	ExDetector SC- 220
37	Bionics Instrument Co. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.bionics-japan.co.jp/en/	GS-1550DP GS-1551DP
39	Bionics Instrument Co. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.bionics-japan.co.jp/en/	GS-1550HT GS-1551HT

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	28.11.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	28.11.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	28.11.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	28.11.2013	(Semiconductor)
U(1)	17.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	17.10.2013	Electrochemical

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Industrial safety equipment, monitoring of gas concentration and warning	0 - 100% LEL	
Industrial safety equipment, monitoring of gas concentration and warning	0 - 100% LEL	
Industrial safety equipment, monitoring of gas concentration and warning	0 - 100% LEL	
Industrial safety equipment, monitoring of gas concentration and warning	0 - 50% LEL	
Continuous monitoring of target gas in hazardous areas	0 - 4000 ppm (Standard) 0 - 1000 ppm (Low)	
Continuous monitoring of target gas in hazardous areas	0 - 4000 ppm (Standard) 0 - 1000 ppm (Low)	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
40	Bionics Instrument Co. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.bionics-japan.co.jp/en/	GS-1550DS GS-1551DS
41	Bionics Instrument Co. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.bionics-japan.co.jp/en/	GS-1550HS GS-1551HS
42	BlueSens gas sensor GmbHHerten, Germany	https://www.bluesens.com	BCP-H2
43	Brechbühler AG Schlieren,CH	https://www.brechbuehler.ch/H2-Sensor.128.0.html	H2 Sensor Series 9000
44	Buveco Gasdetection B.V.Bleiswijk, NL	https://buveco.com/en/	BUCOM ST400EC
45	Buveco Gasdetection B.V.Bleiswijk, NL	https://buveco.com/en/	BUCOM ST650EX

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	17.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	17.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(2)	29.10.2013	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	08.11.2013	(Thermostated flow-through semiconductor type)
U(1)	08.11.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	08.11.2013	Catalytic

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Target gas detection; Production facilities and research centers	0 - 4000 ppm (Standard) 0 - 2000 ppm (Low)	
Target gas detection; Production facilities and research centers	0 - 4000 ppm (Standard) 0 - 2000 ppm (Low)	
Chemical industry, biogas production, agriculture, algal hydrogen production	0 - 10 vol.%, 0 - 50 vol.% 0 - 100 vol.%	
Continuous monitoring of the hydrogen concentration in the GC oven	0.5 vol.% - 4 vol.%	
Target gas detection	0 - 1000 ppm	
Target gas detection	0 - 100% LEL	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
46	CEA Instruments Inc. Westwood,NJ, USA	http://www.ceainstr.com/GAS%20PAGE.html	TRIPLE PLUS +
47	CEA Instruments Inc. Westwood,NJ, USA	http://www.ceainstr.com/GAS%20PAGE.html	TETRA
48	CEA Instruments Inc. Westwood,NJ, USA	http://www.ceainstr.com/GAS%20PAGE.html	GASMAN H2
50	CEA Instruments Inc. Westwood,NJ, USA	http://www.ceainstr.com/GAS%20PAGE.html	SERIES U
51	CEA Instruments Inc. Westwood,NJ, USA	http://www.ceainstr.com/GAS%20PAGE.html	CEA 420
52	CEA Instruments Inc. Westwood,NJ, USA	http://www.ceainstr.com/GAS%20PAGE.html	XGARD Type 1

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	05.12.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	06.11.2013	n/a
U(1)	06.11.2013	n/a
U(1)	17.10.2013	(Solid state diffusion type)
U(1)	17.10.2013	(Solid state diffusion type adsorption - desorption type catalyst surface)
U(1)	17.10.2013	Electrochemical

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Multi-gas unit that simultaneously monitors, displays, and alarms for one to four gases with many different electrochemical sensors available.	0 - 2000 ppm (S01250)0 - 4% (S011971)	
Rechargeable battery powered device. ATEX certified	0 - 2000 ppm	
Personal site monitoring, multi-thread warning system	0 - 2000 ppm, 0 - 100% LEL	
Personal site monitoring, multi-thread warning system	0 - 1000 ppm,0 - 5000 ppm,0 - 20000 ppm (50% LEL), 0 - 100% LEL	
Gas warning system for rooms	0 - 1000 ppm, 0 - 5000 ppm, 0 - 20000 ppm (50% LEL), 0 - 100% LEL	
Gas warning system for rooms	0 - 200 ppm, 0 - 500 ppm, 0 - 2000 ppm, 0 - 2 vol.%, 0 - 4 vol.%	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
53	CEA Instruments Inc. Westwood,NJ, USA	http://www.ceainstr.com/GAS%20PAGE.html	XGARD Type 2
54	CEA Instruments Inc. Westwood,NJ, USA	http://www.ceainstr.com/GAS%20PAGE.html	XGARD Type 3
55	CEA Instruments Inc. Westwood,NJ, USA	http://www.ceainstr.com/GAS%20PAGE.html	XGARD Type 4
56	CEA Instruments Inc. Westwood,NJ, USA	http://www.ceainstr.com/GAS%20PAGE.html	XGARD Type 5
57	CEA Instruments Inc. Westwood,NJ, USA	http://www.ceainstr.com/GAS%20PAGE.html	XGARD Type 6
58	CEA Instruments Inc. Westwood,NJ, USA	http://www.ceainstr.com/GAS%20PAGE.html	TXGARD-IS+

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	17.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	17.10.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	17.10.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	17.10.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	17.10.2013	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	17.10.2013	Electrochemical

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Gas warning system for rooms	0 - 200 ppm, 0 - 500 ppm, 0 - 2000 ppm 0 - 2 vol.%, 0 - 4 vol.%	
Gas warning system for rooms	0 - 100% LEL	
Gas warning system for rooms	0 - 100% LEL	
Gas warning system for rooms	0 - 100% LEL	
Gas warning system for rooms	0 - 5 vol.%, 0 - 10 vol.%, 0 - 50 vol. % (in air) 0 - 20 vol.%, 0 - 25 vol.%, 0 - 30 vol.%(in N2)	
Gas warning system for rooms	2000, 20000 ppm (50% LEL)	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
59	CEA Instruments Inc. Westwood,NJ, USA	http://www.ceainstr.com/GAS%20PAGE.html	FLAMGARD PLUS
61	Citizen Finetech Miyota Co. Ltd.Miyota, Japan	https://cfd.citizen.co.jp/english/sensor/	CGA-1210
62	City Technology Ltd. Portsmouth,UK	https://sps.honeywell.com/us/en/products/advanced-sensing-technologies	3HYE
63	Honeywell (City Technology Ltd. Portsmouth,U)	https://sps.honeywell.com/us/en/products/advanced-sensing-technologies	3HYT
64	City Technology Ltd. Portsmouth,UK	https://sps.honeywell.com/us/en/products/advanced-sensing-technologies	3MHYE
65	Honeywell (City Technology Ltd. Portsmouth,K)	https://sps.honeywell.com/us/en/products/advanced-sensing-technologies	3MHYT

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	17.10.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	28.10.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	17.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	17.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	18.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	18.10.2013	Electrochemical

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Gas warning system for rooms	0 - 100% LEL	
Leakage monitoring of hydrogen fuel cell	200 ppm - 4%	
Industrial Safety	0 - 10000 ppm nominal 20000 ppm max. overload	
Industrial Safety	0 - 1000 ppm nominal 2000 ppm max. overload	
Industrial Safety	0 - 20000 ppm max.	
Industrial Safety	0 - 2000 ppm max.	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensing element
hydrogen sensing element
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
66	City Technology Ltd. Portsmouth,UK	https://sps.honeywell.com/us/en/products/advanced-sensing-technologies	EZT3HYE
67	City Technology Ltd. Portsmouth,UK	https://sps.honeywell.com/us/en/products/advanced-sensing-technologies	EZT3HYT
68	City Technology Ltd. Portsmouth,UK	https://sps.honeywell.com/us/en/products/advanced-sensing-technologies	4HYT
69	City Technology Ltd. Portsmouth,UK	https://sps.honeywell.com/us/en/products/advanced-sensing-technologies	7HYE
70	City Technology Ltd. Portsmouth,UK	https://sps.honeywell.com/us/en/products/advanced-sensing-technologies	7HYT
71	City Technology Ltd. Portsmouth,UK	https://sps.honeywell.com/us/en/products/advanced-sensing-technologies	H2 3E 1%

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	18.10.2013	Electrochemical

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Industrial Safety	0 - 20000 ppm precalibrated Recalibration to intermediate ranges available	
Industrial Safety	0 - 200 ppm, 0 - 300 ppm 0 - 500 ppm, 0 - 1000 ppm, 0 - 2000 ppm precalibrated, Recalibration to intermediate ranges available	
Industrial Safety	0 - 1000 ppm nominal 2000 ppm max. overload	
Industrial Safety	0 - 10000 ppm nominal 20000 ppm max. overload	
Industrial Safety	0 - 1000 ppm nominal 2000 ppm max. overload	
Industrial Safety	0 - 10000 ppm	

Type
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
72	City Technology Ltd. Portsmouth,UK	https://sps.honeywell.com/us/en/products/advanced-sensing-technologies	H2 3E 4%
73	City Technology Ltd. Portsmouth,UK	https://sps.honeywell.com/us/en/products/advanced-sensing-technologies	T3H
74	City Technology Ltd. Portsmouth,UK	https://sps.honeywell.com/us/en/products/advanced-sensing-technologies	T3HYE
76	City Technology Ltd. Portsmouth,UK	https://sps.honeywell.com/us/en/products/advanced-sensing-technologies	T3HYT
77	City Technology Ltd. Portsmouth,UK	https://sps.honeywell.com/us/en/products/advanced-sensing-technologies	4P50M
78	City Technology Ltd. Portsmouth,UK	https://sps.honeywell.com/us/en/products/advanced-sensing-technologies	4P75M

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	18.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	18.10.2013	Catalytic Pellistor
U(1)	18.10.2013	Catalytic Pellistor

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Industrial Safety	0 - 4% (100% LEL)	
Automotive	0 - 300 ppm; eight precalibrated ranges and recalibration to intermediate ranges available	
Automotive	0 - 20000 ppm, 0 - 50000 ppm precalibrated, Recalibration to intermediate ranges available	
Automotive	0 - 2000 ppm; five precalibrated ranges and recalibration to intermediate ranges available	
Critical safety applications	0- 100% LEL	
Hydrogen detection	0 - 100% LEL	

Type
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
79	City Technology Ltd. Portsmouth,UK	https://sps.honeywell.com/us/en/products/advanced-sensing-technologies	4P90M
80	Compur Monitors GmbH & Co. K, München, Germany	https://www.compur.com/en/	Stattox 501
81	Compur Monitors GmbH & Co. KG, München, Germany	https://www.compur.com/en/	Stattox 505
82	Control Instruments Corporation Fairfield,NJ, USA	https://www.controlinstruments.com/products/gas-sensors	SNR476
83	COSA Xentaur Yaphank,NY, USA	https://cosaxentaur.com/	CHAContinuous Hydrogen Analyzer
87	Crowcon Detection Instruments Ltd. Abingdon UK	https://www.crowcon.com/de/product-category/portables/	TRIPLE PLUS +

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	18.10.2013	Catalytic Pellistor
U(1)	28.11.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	28.11.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	08.11.2013	Electrochemical, Micro fuel cell
U(1)	05.12.2013	Electrochemical Potentiometric proton conducting polymer membrane
U(1)	05.12.2013	Electrochemical

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Combustible gas sensor	0 - 100% LEL	
Stationary Gas Warning System	0 - 150 / 300 / 1000 ppm	
Stationary Gas Warning System	300 ppm, 1000 ppm	
Monitoring of hydrogen gas	0 - 1000 ppm (standard range; 0 - 2000 ppm available)	
Refining, petrochemical, electric power applications; Hydrogen production, hydrogen-cooled power generation; Hydrogen/hydrocarbon ratio, isomerization	0.04 - 100 vol.%	
Monitoring and portable safety applications	0 - 100% LEL	

Type
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
88	Crowcon Detection Instruments Ltd. Abingdon UK	https://www.crowcon.com/de/product-category/portables/	FLAMGARD PLUS
89	Crowcon Detection Instruments Ltd. Abingdon UK	https://www.crowcon.com/de/product-category/portables/	TXGARD-IS+
90	Crowcon Detection Instruments Ltd. Abingdon UK	https://www.crowcon.com/de/product-category/portables/	40/40 Series Flame Detector
91	C-Squared Inc. Anaheim, CA, USA	http://www.c-squaredinc.com/	Hycision 10M
92	C-Squared Inc. Anaheim, CA, USA	http://www.c-squaredinc.com/	Hycision 100M
93	C-Squared Inc. Anaheim, CA, USA	http://www.c-squaredinc.com/	Hycision 10

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	05.12.2013	Catalytic Pellistor
U(1)	05.12.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	05.12.2013	Optical (IR based)
U(1)	18.10.2013	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	18.10.2013	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	18.10.2013	Thermal conductivity

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Oxygen, toxic and flammable gas detection with local display and optional relays	0 - 100% LEL	
Oxygen, toxic and flammable gas detection with local display and optional relays	2000 ppm, 50% LEL, 100% LEL	
Hydrogen sensing	n/a	Flame detection
Hydrogen sensing	0 - 10 vol.%	
Hydrogen sensing	0 - 100 vol.%	
Hydrogen analyser for the Automotive, Industrial, Diving, Medical and Safety Monitoring Markets	0 - 10 vol.%	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
n/a
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
94	C-Sqared Inc. Anaheim, CA, USA	http://www.c-squaredinc.com/	Hycision 100
96	DET-TRONICS Minneapolis, MN, USA	https://www.det-tronics.com/	GT3000
97	DET-TRONICS Minneapolis, MN, USA	https://www.det-tronics.com/	X3302
98	Dextens SA Geneva, Switzerland	http://www.dextens.ch/About_Us.html	H2 52201
101	Dräger Safety AG & Co. KGaA Lübeck, Germany	https://www.draeger.com/de_de/Home	DrägerSensor® XS P/N 68 09 185
102	Dräger Safety AG & Co. KGaA Lübeck, Germany	https://www.draeger.com/de_de/Home	DrägerSensor® XS P/N 68 11 365

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	18.10.2013	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	18.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	18.10.2013	Optical (IR spectroscopy)
U(1)	28.08.2014	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	19.04.2022	Electrochemical
U(1)	19.04.2022	Electrochemical

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Hydrogen analyser for the Automotive, Industrial, Diving, Medical and Safety Monitoring Markets	0 - 100 vol.%	
Gas leak detection, continuous monitoring of atmosphere	0 - 1000 ppm	
Hydrogen fire/flame detection in e.g. refineries, chemical loading, battery rooms, compressor areas, generators, refrigerants, gas plants.	n/a	
Also for hydrogen solved in liquids	0-2 ppm, 0-10 ppm	
Detection of toxic gases and vapours, P/N for hydrogen-specific sensor head	0 - 2000 ppm	
Detection of toxic gases and vapours, P/N for hydrogen-specific sensor head	0 - 4.0 vol.%	

Type
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
103	Dräger Safety AG & Co. KGaA Lübeck, Germany	https://www.draeger.com/de_de/Home	Polytron SE Ex PR ... DD
105	Dräger Safety AG & Co. KGaA Lübeck, Germany	https://www.draeger.com/de_de/Home	Polytron SE Ex LC ... DD
106	Dräger Safety AG & Co. KGaA Lübeck, Germany	https://www.draeger.com/de_de/Home	PolytronSE Ex HT M DD
107	Dräger Safety AG & Co. KGaA Lübeck, Germany	https://www.draeger.com/de_de/Home	Polytron 3000
108	Element One Inc. Boulder,CO, USA	https://elem1.com/visual-hydrogen-detection/	DetecTape H2
109	ENMET Corp. Ann Arbor, MI, USA	https://enmet.com/	EX 5100

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	28.10.2013	Catalytic Pellistor
U(1)	28.10.2013	Catalytic Pellistor
U(1)	28.10.2013	Catalytic Pellistor
U(2)	30.10.2013	Catalytic Pellistor
U(1)		Optical Chemochromic
U(1)	31.10.2013	Catalytic Pellistor

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Continuous monitoring of combustible gases and vapours in ambient air.	n/a	
Continuous monitoring of combustible gases and vapours in ambient air; Target gases: hydrogen, etc.	n/a	
Continuous monitoring of combustible gases and vapours in ambient air; Target gases: hydrogen, etc.	n/a	
Continuous monitoring of toxic gases in ambient air; gases: hydrogen etc.	various, not specified	
Leak detection apparatus Storage Tanks, Connectors, Fuel Cells, Fuel Reformers, Connection Hardware, Grounding Connections, Hoses, and anywhere hydrogen is used.	n/a	
Combustable gas sensor	0 - 100% LEL	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensing element
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
110	ENMET Corp. Ann Arbor, MI, USA	https://enmet.com/	EX 5175P/N 10014-1500
111	ENMET Corp. Ann Arbor, MI, USA	https://enmet.com/	SDS-1500-97D
112	ENMET Corp. Ann Arbor, MI, USA	https://enmet.com/	ProAir 2200
113	ENMET Corp. Ann Arbor, MI, USA	https://enmet.com/	GSM 60
114	ENMET Corp. Ann Arbor, MI, USA	https://enmet.com/	PGD2
116	Environment One Corporation Niskayuna, NY, USA	https://eone.com/	GGA

U	Acc date	Technology
U(2)	31.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(2)	31.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	31.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	31.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	31.10.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	18.10.2013	Thermal conductivity

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Hydrogen oxygen and toxic gas detection	24 ppm (LDL) - 2000 ppm	
Hydrogen oxygen and toxic gas detection	24 ppm (LDL) - 2000 ppm	
Hydrogen oxygen and toxic gas detection	0 - 2000 ppm	
Hydrogen oxygen and toxic gas detection	0 - 2000 ppm	
Hydrogen, oxygen and toxic gas detection	customised ranges	
Hydrogen-cooled generators, continuous monitoring of gas purity during all phases of generator operation	70 - 100% H2 in air 0 - 100% H2 in CO2	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
117	Environment One Corporation Niskayuna, NY, USA	https://eone.com/	PGA
118	ESCUBE GmbH & Co. KG Stuttgart, Germany	https://www.lamtec.de/unternehmen/escube-gmbh-co-kg.html	HydroSEN
119	ExTox Gasmess-Systeme GmbH, Unna, Germany	https://www.extox.de/	H2-2-EC
120	ExTox Gasmess-Systeme GmbH, Unna, Germa	https://www.extox.de/	H2-30-WLD
121	ExTox Gasmess-Systeme GmbH, Una, Germany	https://www.extox.de/	H2-1000-EC
122	ExTox Gasmess-Systeme GmbH, Unna, Germany	https://www.extox.de/	BG-HL

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	18.10.2013	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	18.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(2)	18.10.2013	Metal oxide semiconductor

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
non-hazardous environments	70 - 100% H2 in air 0 - 100% H2 in CO2	
Safety and leak monitoring applications, e.g. of fuel cells or electrolysers	0 - 1000 ppm / 0 - 10000 ppm (max. 50% LEL)	
Industrial	0 - 2 vol.%	
Industrial; main application: gas analysis in combination with gas withdrawal system	0 - 30 vol.%	
Bio gas analysis	0 - 1000 ppm	
Ambient air monitoring, etc.	0 - 100% LEL	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensing element
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
124	ExTox Gasmess-Systeme GmbH, Unna, Germany	https://www.extox.de/	BG-5000-HL
125	ExTox Gasmess-Systeme GmbH, Unna, Germany	https://www.extox.de/	BG-WT
129	Figaro USA Inc. Glenview,IL, USA	https://www.figaro.com/?	TGS821
130	Figaro USA Inc. Glenview,IL, USA	https://www.figaro.com/?	TGS813
131	Figaro USA Inc. Glenview,IL, USA	https://www.figaro.com/?	TGS6812
132	FIS Inc. Hyogo, Japan	http://www.fisinc.co.jp/company/	SB-19-00

U	Acc date	Technology
U(2)	18.10.2013	(Metal oxide semiconductor)
U(2)	18.10.2013	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	25.09.2013	Resistive Semiconductor (SnO2)
U(1)	10.12.2013	Resistive Semiconductor (SnO2)
U(1)	25.09.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	18.10.2013	Resistive Semiconductor (SnO2)

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Leakage and trace analysis, etc.	0 - 5000 ppm	
Explosion protection	0 - 100% LEL	
Hydrogen gas detection for transformer maintenance, batteries, steel industry usage, etc.	50 ppm - 1000 ppm	
Domestic gas leak detectors and alarms, portable gas detectors	500 ppm -10000 ppm	
Hydrogen and combustible gas leak detector for fuel cells/stationary fuel cell systems; Detection of hydrogen, methane and LP gas	0 - 100% LEL	
hydrogen detection	n/a	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensing element

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
133	FIS Inc. Hyogo, Japan	http://www.fisinc.co.jp/company/	SP-19-01
134	FIS Inc. Hyogo, Japan	http://www.fisinc.co.jp/company/	SB-42A-11
144	GFG Dortmund, Germany	https://www.gfgsafet.com/int/	GMA36 Pro
145	GFG Dortmund, Germany	https://www.gfgsafet.com/int/	Micro IV
146	GFG Dortmund, Germany	https://www.gfgsafet.com/int/	Microtector II G460
147	H2Scan Corp. Valencia, CA, USA	https://www.h2scan.com/	HY-ALERTA 500

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	07.06.2022	Resistive Semiconductor (SnO2)
U(1)	07.06.2022	Semiconductor
U(1)	08.11.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	08.11.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	08.11.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	15.10.2013	Two sensor elements: Work function MOS capacitor & Resistive Pd/Ni thin film resistor

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
hydrogen detection	0 ppm to 2000 ppm	
Hydrogen detection in fuel cells / automotive	0.1 Vol-% to 2 Vol-%	
Continuous surveillance of toxic gases, oxygen and hydrogen	0 - 2000 ppm 0 - 1 vol.% 0 - 4 vol.%	0 - 1
Single gas detection of toxic gases, oxygen and hydrogen	2000 ppm 4 vol.%	4
Continuous and selective measurement of seven gases simultaneously	0 - 2000 ppm 0 - 1 vol.% 4 vol.%	0 -
Portable hydrogen leak detector; locating source of hydrogen leak where hydrogen gas is produced, used, transported, or stored	15 ppm - 100 vol.%	

Type
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
148	H2Scan Corp. Valencia, CA, USA	https://www.h2scan.com/	HY-ALERTA 600
149	H2Scan Corp. Valencia, CA, USA	https://www.h2scan.com/	HY-ALERTA 1600
150	H2Scan Corp. Valencia, CA, USA	https://www.h2scan.com/	HY-ALERTA 2600
151	H2Scan Corp. Valencia, CA, USA	https://www.h2scan.com/	HY-OPTIMA 2700AS
152	H2Scan Corp. Valencia, CA, USA	https://www.h2scan.com/	HY-OPTIMA 2700
153	H2Scan Corp. Valencia, CA, USA	https://www.h2scan.com/	HY-OPTIMA 2720

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	15.10.2013	Resistive Pd/Ni thin film resistor
U(1)	15.10.2013	Resistive Pd/Ni thin film resistor
U(1)	15.10.2013	Resistive Pd/Ni thin film resistor
U(1)	10.12.2013	Resistive Pd/Ni thin film resistor
U(1)	15.10.2013	Resistive Pd/Ni thin film resistor
U(1)	15.10.2013	Resistive Pd/Ni thin film resistor

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Hydrogen-specific leak detection and measurement	0.4 - 5 vol.% 125% LFL	10 -
Hydrogen-specific leak detection and measurement	0.4 - 5 vol.% 125% LFL	10 -
Hydrogen-specific leak detection and measurement	0.4 - 5 vol.% 10 - 125% LFL	
Process hydrogen measurement in refineries, chemical plants, air separation units and industrial gas manufacturing plants	0.5 - 100 vol.% (@ 1 ATM)	
Ideal for hydrogen production and petrochemical applications (where real-time measurements of hydrogen can enhance process plant efficiencies, diagnostics and maintenance management)	0.5 - 100 vol.% (@ 1 ATM)	
Ideal for hydrogen processes (where real-time measurements of hydrogen can ensure safety in application, increase process efficiencies, improve diagnostics and enhance maintenance management)	0.4 - 5 vol.% (@ 1ATM)	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
155	H2Scan Corp. Valencia,CA, USA	https://www.h2scan.com/	HY-OPTIMA 2730
156	H2Scan Corp. Valencia,CA, USA	https://www.h2scan.com/	HY-OPTIMA 2740
157	H2Scan Corp. Valencia,CA, USA	https://www.h2scan.com/	HY-OPTIMA 1700AS
158	H2Scan Corp. Valencia,CA, USA	https://www.h2scan.com/	HY-OPTIMA 1700
159	H2Scan Corp. Valencia,CA, USA	https://www.h2scan.com/	HY-OPTIMA 1720
161	H2Scan Corp. Valencia,CA, USA	https://www.h2scan.com/	HY-OPTIMA 1730

①	Acc date	Technology
①(1)	15.10.2013	Resistive Pd/Ni thin film resistor
①(1)	15.10.2013	Resistive Pd/Ni thin film resistor
①(1)	15.10.2013	Resistive Pd/Ni thin film resistor
①(1)	15.10.2013	Resistive Pd/Ni thin film resistor
①(1)	15.10.2013	Resistive Pd/Ni thin film resistor
①(1)	15.10.2013	Resistive Pd/Ni thin film resistor

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Ideal for hydrogen production and petrochemical applications (where real-time measurements of hydrogen can increase process plant efficiencies, improve diagnostics and enhance maintenance management)	0.5 - 100 vol.% (@ 1 ATM)	
Ideal for hydrogen processes (where real-time measurements of hydrogen can ensure safety in application, increase process efficiencies, improve diagnostics and enhance maintenance management)	0.5 - 100 vol.% (@ 1 ATM)	
Process hydrogen measurement in refineries, chemical plants, air separation units and industrial gas manufacturing plants	0.5 - 100 vol.% (@ 1 ATM)	
Ideal for process gas streams containing virtually no contaminants (where real time continuous measurements of hydrogen can increase process plant efficiencies, improve diagnostics and enhance maintenance management)	0.5 - 100 vol.% (@ 1 ATM)	
Ideal for the detection of hydrogen within processes (where real-time monitoring can increase plant safety, improve process diagnostics and enhance maintenance management)	0.4 - 5 vol.% (@ 1ATM)	
Ideal for hydrogen gas production, petroleum refining and petrochemical applications (where continuous real time measurements of hydrogen can increase process plant efficiencies, improve diagnostics and enhance maintenance management)	0.5 - 100 vol.% (@ 1 ATM)	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
162	H2Scan Corp. Valencia,CA, USA	https://www.h2scan.com/	HY-OPTIMA 1740
163	H2Scan Corp. Valencia,CA, USA	https://www.h2scan.com/	HY-OPTIMA 700
164	H2Scan Corp. Valencia,CA, USA	https://www.h2scan.com/	HY-OPTIMA 720AS-GC
165	H2Scan Corp. Valencia,CA, USA	https://www.h2scan.com/	HY-OPTIMA 720
166	H2Scan Corp. Valencia, CA, USA	https://www.h2scan.com/	HY-OPTIMA 730
168	H2Scan Corp. Valencia, CA, USA	https://www.h2scan.com/	HY-OPTIMA 740

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	15.10.2013	Resistive Pd/Ni thin film resistor
U(1)	15.10.2013	Resistive Pd/Ni thin film resistor
U(1)	10.12.2013	Resistive Pd/Ni thin film resistor
U(1)	15.10.2013	Resistive Pd/Ni thin film resistor
U(1)	15.10.2013	Resistive Pd/Ni thin film resistor
U(1)	15.10.2013	Resistive Pd/Ni alloy thin film resistor

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Ideal for hydrogen gas production, petroleum refining and petrochemical applications(where real-time measurements can enhance process plant efficiencies, diagnostics and maintenance management	0.5 - 100 vol.% (@ 1 ATM)	
Ideal for hydrogen production and petrochemical applications(where real-time measurements can enhance process plant efficiencies, diagnostics and maintenance management)	0.5 - 100 vol.% (@ 1 ATM)	
Hydrogen Analyzing System to detect, measure and respond to hydrogen leaks in gas chromatography (GC) systems.	0.5 - 5 vol.% (@ 1 ATM)	
Ideal for monitoring of hydrogen processes (where real-time measurements can ensure safety in application, increase process efficiencies, improve diagnostics and enhance maintenance management)	0.4 - 5 vol.% (@ 1ATM)	
Ideal for hydrogen production and petrochemical applications(where real-time measurements can enhance process plant efficiencies, diagnostics and maintenance management)	0.5 - 100 vol.% (@ 1 ATM)	
Ideal for hydrogen production and petrochemical applications(where real-time measurements can enhance process plant efficiencies, diagnostics and maintenance management)	0.5 - 100 vol.% (@ 1 ATM)	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
170	Henan Hanwei Electronics Co. Zhengzhou, China	https://www.hwsensor.com/	MQ-2
171	Henan Hanwei Electronics Co. Zhengzhou, China	https://www.hwsensor.com/	MQ-8
172	Honeywell Analytics Uster, CH	https://sps.honeywell.com/	MIDAS
173	Honeywell Analytics Uster, CH	https://sps.honeywell.com/	Apex
174	Honeywell Analytics Uster, CH	https://sps.honeywell.com/	Sensepoint Combustible
175	Honeywell Analytics Uster, CH	https://sps.honeywell.com/	Sensepoint Toxic

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	18.10.2013	Resistive Semiconductor (SnO2)
U(1)	19.04.2022	(Semiconductor)
U(2)	10.12.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	16.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	16.10.2013	Catalytic Poison resistant bead
U(1)	16.10.2013	Electrochemical

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Combustible gas sensor	300 - 5000 ppm	
Hydrogen gas sensor	n/a	
Typical industrial process environment; for gases used or generated in the semiconductor and other industrial manufacturing applications	0 - 100% LEL 0 - 1000 ppm	
Petrochemical: exploration drilling rigs Heavy industrial: Steel manufacture, Manufacturing: Automotive, Pharmaceutical: research labs	0 ppm - 1000 ppm	
Indoor, outdoor, potentially explosive environments	0 - 100% LEL 0 - 10% LEL	
Indoor, outdoor, potentially explosive environments	0 - 1000 ppm 0 - 10000 ppm	

Type
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
177	Honeywell Analytics Uster, CH	https://sps.honeywell.com/	Satellite XT
178	Honeywell Analytics Uster CH	https://sps.honeywell.com/	E3Point
181	Industrial Scientific Oakdale PA USA	https://www.indsci.com/en/contact?hsLang=en	Ventis MX4
182	Industrial Scientific Oakdale PA USA	https://www.indsci.com/en/contact?hsLang=en	BM 25
183	Industrial Scientific Oakdale PA USA	https://www.indsci.com/en/contact?hsLang=en	GasBadge Pro
184	Industrial Scientific Oakdale PA USA	https://www.indsci.com/en/contact?hsLang=en	MX4 iQuad

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	16.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	23.10.2013	Catalytic
U(2)	31.10.2013	Catalytic
U(2)	31.10.2013	Catalytic Electrochemical
U(2)	31.10.2013	n/a
U(1)	19.04.2022	Catalytic

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Typical installation: gas cabinet exhaust ducting, equipment enclosures.	0 - 1.0 vol.% 0 - 4.0 vol.%	
Gas monitoring	0 - 100% LEL	
Chemical, Construction, Electrical / Gas Utilities, Fire Service, Oil and Gas, Public Works, Steel Production, Water / Waste Water Treatment Industries	0 - 100% LEL (Combustible gas sensor)	
Area monitoring	0 - 100% LEL (Combustible gas sensor) 0 - 2000 ppm (Hydrogen sensor)	
Single gas monitoring	0 - 2000 ppm	
Personal gas monitor	0 - 100% LEL (Combustible gas sensor)	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
187	INFICON Bad Ragaz, Schweiz	https://www.inficon.com/en-us/nav-products/Category/ProductGroup/pg-LeakDetectors	Sensistor-ILS500
188	INFICON Bad Ragaz, Schweiz	https://www.inficon.com/en-us/nav-products/Category/ProductGroup/pg-LeakDetectors	Sensistor- XRS9012
189	INFICON Bad Ragaz, Schweiz	https://www.inficon.com/en-us/nav-products/Category/ProductGroup/pg-LeakDetectors	Extrima
190	INFICON Bad Ragaz, Schweiz	https://www.inficon.com/en-us/nav-products/Category/ProductGroup/pg-LeakDetectors	Sensistor- ISH2000
191	INFICON Bad Ragaz, Schweiz	https://www.inficon.com/en-us/nav-products/Category/ProductGroup/pg-LeakDetectors	Sensistor-Sentrac
273	Kebaili Corp.	https://www.kebaili.com/	KHS-EVAL-L-LEL

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	17.09.2014	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Leak detection	0.7 ppm H2 in air	
Leak detection	0.7 ppm H2 in air	
Leak detection	0.7 ppm H2 in air	
Leak detection	0.5 ppm H2 ; 5×10^{-7} mbar l/s or cc/s with 5% H2	
Leak detection	0.5 ppm H2 ; 5×10^{-7} mbarl/s	
Hydrogen detection	0 - 100% LEL (0 - 40000 ppm)	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
274	Kebaili Corp.	https://www.kebaili.com/	KHS-EVAL-L-PPM
275	Kebaili Corp.	https://www.kebaili.com/	KHS-EVAL-S-LEL
276	Komyo Rikagaku Kogyo K. K. Kawasaki,Japan	https://www.komyok.co.jp/en/product/03/004/9104.html	RD-4
277	Komyo Rikagaku Kogyo K. K. Kawasaki,Japan	https://www.komyok.co.jp/en/	FA-480 / FA-490
279	Komyo Rikagaku Kogyo K. K. Kawasaki,Japan	https://www.komyok.co.jp/en/	137U
282	KWJ Engineering Inc. Newark,CA, USA	https://www.kwjengineering.com/	626 Pipeline Special

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	15.07.2022	Catalytic
U(3)	20.04.2022	Hot wire semiconductor
U(1)	05.11.2013	Optical (colour change)
U(1)	28.10.2013	conductometric

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Hydrogen detection	0 - 10% LEL (0 - 4000 ppm)	
Hydrogen detection	0 - 100% LEL (0 - 40000 ppm)	
For use in Fixed Type Gas Detector Alarm Systems (e.g. FA-480, FA-490)	n/a	
Single point gas leak detection	0 - 2000 ppm	
Leak detection	0.05 - 0.8 vol. %	
Gas pipeline leak surveys, above and below ground	0 ppm - 10000 ppm	

Type
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensing element
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
283	KWJ Engineering Inc. Newark,CA, USA	https://www.kwjengineering.com/	634 Pro Surveyor
285	Kyushu University, Kato-Lab / Orii&Mec Corporation Fukuoka, Japan	http://uhs-eng.kato-lab.org/link	H2 Sensor
286	LAMTEC GmbH & Co KG Walldorf, Germany	https://www.lamtec.de/index.php?id=2	CarboSen
288	LAMTEC GmbH & Co KG Walldorf, Germany	https://www.lamtec.de/index.php?id=2	HydroSen
289	LFE GmbH & Co. KG Bruchköbel, Germany	https://www.lfe.de/de/	CONTHOS 3
291	Materion GmbH Wismar, Germany	https://www.materion-gmbh.de/	MOHS 2.1

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	28.10.2013	conductometric
U(1)	07.06.2022	Acoustic Ultrasonic
U(1)	01.11.2013	Electrochemical Solid state electrolyte
U(1)	01.11.2013	Electrochemical Solid state electrolyte
U(2)	11.12.2013	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	21.10.2013	Optical

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Gas pipeline leak surveys, above and below ground	0 - 10000 ppm	
Portable, installation and large area multipoint	100 ppm - 100%	
Detection of oxidisable Co/H2 gas constituents in gases. Monitoring of combustion process	n/a	
Leakage and safety monitoring particularly of fuel cells and electrolysis equipment	0 - 1000 ppm, 0 - 10000 ppm(max. 50% LEL)	
industrial processes	Lowest: 0 - 0.5% H2 in N2 or 99.5 - 100% H2 in N2 Largest: 0 - 100% H2	
Room air monitoring, process control, control of industrial applications	0.1 - 4.0 vol.%	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
292	Materion GmbH Wismar, Germany	https://www.materion-gmbh.de/	MOHS 2.2
293	Materion GmbH Wismar, Germany	https://www.materion-gmbh.de/	MOHS 3
294	Materion GmbH Wismar, Germany	https://www.materion-gmbh.de/	MOHS 3.Z
295	Materion GmbH Wismar, Germany	https://www.materion-gmbh.de/	MOHS 4
296	Membrapor Wallisellen, CH	https://www.membrapor.ch/	H2/M-1000
297	Membrapor Wallisellen, CH	https://www.membrapor.ch/	H2/M-4000

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	21.10.2013	Optical
U(1)	21.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	21.10.2013	Electrochemical

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Room air monitoring, process control, control of industrial applications	0.1 - 4.0 vol.%	
Room air monitoring, process control, control of industrial applications	0.1 - 100 vol.%	
Room air monitoring, process control, control of industrial applications	0.1 - 100 vol.%	
Room air monitoring, process control, control of industrial applications	0.1 - 100 vol.%	
Safety and Environmental Control For Portable Gas Detectors	0 - 1000 ppm	
Safety and Environmental Control For Portable Gas Detectors	0 - 4000 ppm	

Type
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
298	Membrapor Wallisellen, CH	https://www.membrapor.ch/	H2/CA-1000
299	Membrapor Wallisellen, CH	https://www.membrapor.ch/	H2/CB-1000
300	Membrapor Wallisellen, CH	https://www.membrapor.ch/	H2/C-2000
301	Membrapor Wallisellen, CH	https://www.membrapor.ch/	H2/C-5000
302	Membrapor Wallisellen, CH	https://www.membrapor.ch/	H2/C-20000
303	Membrapor Wallisellen, CH	https://www.membrapor.ch/	H2/CT-40000

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	21.10.2013	Electrochemical

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Medical Applications, Safety and Environmental Control	0 - 1000 ppm	
Medical Applications Safety and Environmental Control	0 - 1000 ppm	
Safety and Environmental Control	0 - 2000 ppm	
Safety and Environmental Control	0 - 5000 ppm	
Safety and Environmental Control	0 - 20000 ppm	
Safety and Environmental Control	0 - 40000 ppm	

Type
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
304	Membrapor Wallisellen, CH	https://www.membrapor.ch/	H2/SA-1000
305	Membrapor Wallisellen, CH	https://www.membrapor.ch/	H2/S-2000
306	Membrapor Wallisellen, CH	https://www.membrapor.ch/	H2/SA-1000-S
308	Membrapor Wallisellen, CH	https://www.membrapor.ch/	H2/S-2000-S
309	Membrapor Wallisellen, CH	https://www.membrapor.ch/	H2/S-10000-S
310	Micronas GmbH Freiburg, Germany	https://www.micronas.tdk.com/en/products/gas-sensors	GAS 8616B

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	21.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	06.11.2013	Work function Capacity-coupled field effect transistor / MOSFET

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Safety and Environmental Control	0 - 1000 ppm	
Safety and Environmental Control	0 - 2000 ppm	
Medical Applications Safety and Environmental Control	0 - 1000 ppm	
Safety and Environmental Control	0 - 2000 ppm	
Safety and Process Control	0 - 10000 ppm	
Detection of concentration changes of ambient trace gases, trace gas / gas leakage detection	100 ppb - 1% gas concentration approx.	

Type
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
311	Microsens S.A. Neuchâtel,CH	http://microsens.ch/products/gas.htm	MCGS
312	Microsens S.A. Neuchâtel,C	http://microsens.ch/products/gas.htm	MSGs 3000
313	Microsens S.A. Neuchâtel,C	http://microsens.ch/products/gas.htm	MSGs 4000
314	Microsens S.A. Neuchâtel,C	http://microsens.ch/products/gas.htm	MGSM 3000
318	MSA Cranberry Township,PA, USAMSA Auer Gm bH Berlin,Germany	https://de.msasafety.com/Portable-Gas-Detection/c/114?isLanding=true	ULTIMA® XE Hydrogen
319	MSA Cranberry Township,PA, USAMSA Auer Gm bH Berlin,German	https://de.msasafety.com/Portable-Gas-Detection/c/114?isLanding=true	ULTIMA® XE Combustible gas

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	21.10.2013	Resistive (Semiconducting metal oxide layer)
U(1)	21.10.2013	Resistive (Semiconducting metal oxide layer)
U(1)	21.10.2013	Resistive (Semiconducting metal oxide layer)
U(1)	29.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	29.10.2013	Catalytic

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Security (explosive gases, solvents), industrial process monitoring	0 - 100% LEL	
Security (explosive gases, solvents), industrial process monitoring, indoor air quality, combustion control, environment,exhaust gases	1 - 10000 ppm	
Security (explosive gases, solvents), industrial process monitoring, indoor air quality, combustion control, environment,exhaust gases	1 - 10000 ppm	
Pre-calibrated module for portable systems, Indoor air monitoring, Environment monitoring, Security, industrial process control	1 - 10000 ppm	
Continuous detection and monitoring of combustible gases, industrial environment Hydrogen monitoring in Data Centers, Refineries, Chemical/Petrochemical	0 - 1000 ppm	
Continuous detection and monitoring of combustible gases, industrial environment Hydrogen monitoring in Data Centers, Refineries, Chemical/Petrochemical	0 - 100% LEL	

Type
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
320	MSA Cranberry Township,PA, US MSA Auer GmbH Berlin,German	https://de.msasafety.com/Portable-Gas-Detection/c/114?isLanding=true	TRIGARD®
321	MSA Cranberry Township,PA, US MSA Auer GmbH Berlin,German	https://de.msasafety.com/Portable-Gas-Detection/c/114?isLanding=true	GasGard® XL
323	MSA Cranberry Township,PA, US MSA Auer GmbH Berlin,German	https://de.msasafety.com/Portable-Gas-Detection/c/114?isLanding=true	Ultrasonic IS-5 / E
324	MST Intertrade GmbH München,Germany	http://www.mst-it.com/eng	SECS H2 20000
325	MST Intertrade GmbH München,German	http://www.mst-it.com/eng	Hydrogen-H2-2E- 5%
326	MST Intertrade GmbH München,German	http://www.mst-it.com/eng	H2 Sensor 4 Se 6-24

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	11.12.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	11.12.2013	n/a
U(1)	11.12.2013	Acoustic (ultrasound)
U(1)	20.04.2022	Electrochemical
U(1)	20.04.2022	Electrochemical
U(1)	20.04.2022	Electrochemical

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Detection of combustible gases, including hydrogen	n/a	
Combustible, Oxygen, Toxic gas Detection controller	n/a	
Gas leak detection; gas pipelines, hydrogen storage	25 kHz to 70 kHz (Frequency range) 58 dB to 104 dB (Ultrasonic dynamic range)	
Hydrogen detection	0 - 20000 ppm	
Hydrogen detection	0 - 5 vol.% in air or N2	
Hydrogen detection	0 - 20000 ppm	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
327	Nano Environmental Technology (N.E.T.) S.r.l. Cornaredo,Italy	https://www.nenvitech.com/	NP-17SMM
328	Nano Environmental Technology (N.E.T.) S.r.l. Cornaredo,Italy	https://www.nenvitech.com/	NP-17SM
329	Nano Environmental Technology (N.E.T.) S.r.l. Cornaredo,Italy	https://www.nenvitech.com/	NP-17SHM NP-17SHP
330	Nano Environmental Technology (N.E.T.) S.r.l. Cornaredo,Italy	https://www.nenvitech.com/	NP-18SMM
331	Nano Environmental Technology (N.E.T.) S.r.l. Cornaredo,Italy	https://www.nenvitech.com/	NP-18SHM NP-18SHP
333	Nano Environmental Technology (N.E.T.) S.r.l. Cornaredo,Italy	https://www.nenvitech.com/	NP-30SHM NP-30SHP

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	12.12.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	12.12.2013	Catalytic Pellistor
U(2)	12.12.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	12.12.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	12.12.2013	Catalytic
U(2)	12.12.2013	Catalytic

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Flammable gas detection	0 - 100% LEL	
Flammable gas detection	0 - 100% LEL	
Flammable gas detection	0 - 100% LEL (linear to 60% LEL)	
Flammable gas detection	0 - 100% LEL	
Flammable gas detection	0 - 100% LEL (linear to 60% LEL)	
Flammable gas detection	0 - 100% LEL	

Type
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
337	Nano Environmental Technology (N.E.T.) S.r.l. Cornaredo,Italy	https://www.nenvitech.com/	Genius
338	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NC-170 (NCP-170)
339	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NC-170S (NCP- 170S)
341	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NC-300 (NCP-300)
342	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NC-300S (NCP- 300S)
343	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NC-180 (NCP-180)

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	28.10.2013	Two sensor elements: Optical (IR) and Catalytic
U(1)	21.10.2013	Pellistor

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Hydrocarbon and hydrogen detection 0-100% LEL	0 - 100% LEL (hydrogen)	
Industrial sensor	Less than 100% LEL	
Industrial sensor	Less than 100% LEL	
Industrial sensor	Less than 100% LEL	
Industrial sensor	Less than 100% LEL	
Industrial sensor	Less than 100% LEL	

Type
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
344	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NC-180S-H (NCP-180S-H)
345	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NC-180-H (NCP- 180-H)
346	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NC-50S (NCP-50S)
347	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NC-70S (NCP-70S)
348	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NAP-2A
349	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NAP-55A

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	21.10.2013	Pellistor
U(1)	12.12.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	12.12.2013	Catalytic

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Industrial sensor	Less than 100% LEL	
Industrial sensor	Less than 100% LEL	
Industrial sensor	Less than 100% LEL	
Industrial sensor	Less than 100% LEL	
Residential sensor; Gas detectors, gas densitometers	Hydrogen: 0.05 - 4%, 0.05 - 1.5% (high accuracy)	
Residential sensor; Gas detectors, leak testers	Hydrogen: 0.05 - 4%, 0.05 - 1.5% (high accuracy)	

Type
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
350	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NAP-56A
351	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NAP-50A
352	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NAP-50AF
353	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NAP-3A
354	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NAP-66A
355	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NAP-67A

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	12.12.2013	Catalytic
U(1)		Catalytic

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Residential sensor	Hydrogen: 0.05 - 4%, 0.05 - 1.5% (high accuracy)	
Residential sensor; Gas detectors	Hydrogen: 0.05 - 4%, 0.05 - 1.5% (high accuracy)	
Residential sensor	Hydrogen: 0.05 - 4%, 0.05 - 1.5% (high accuracy)	
Residential sensor; LP Gas detectors, leakage tester, gas denistometers	Hydrogen: 0.05 - 4%, 0.05 - 1.5% (high accuracy)	
Residential sensor; Gas detectors, leak testers	Hydrogen: 0.05 - 4%, 0.05 - 1.5% (high accuracy)	
Residential sensor	Hydrogen: 0.05 - 4%, 0.05 - 1.5% (high accuracy)	

Type
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
356	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NAP-100AM
357	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NAP-100AC
358	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NAP-100AD
359	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NAP-100AH
360	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NSU-131A
362	NEMOTO Sensor Engineering Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://www.nemoto.co.jp/	NSU-131AF

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	12.12.2013	Catalytic

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Industrial	1 - 50% LEL	
Industrial	3 - 100% LEL	
Industrial	1 - 50% LEL	
Industrial	1 - 50% LEL (Hydrogen)	
Residential sensor, for hydrogen fuel cell, pre-set alarm calibration	Calibrated Alarm Concentration: 3600 - 4000 ppm Calibration Range: 5 - 25% LEL(Hydrogen)	
Residential sensor, for hydrogen fuel cell, pre-set alarm calibration	Calibrated Alarm Concentration: 3600 - 4000 ppm Calibration Range: 5 - 25% LEL(Hydrogen)	

Type
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
363	Neodym Systems Inc. Vancouver,Canada	http://www.neodymsystems.com/	HydroKnowz®
364	Neodym Systems Inc. Vancouver,Canada	http://www.neodymsystems.com/	ProtiSen®
365	Neodym Systems Inc. Vancouver,Canada	http://www.neodymsystems.com/	PowerKnowz®
366	Neodym Systems Inc. Vancouver,Canada	http://www.neodymsystems.com/	MiniKnowz®
370	New Cosmos Electric Co. Ltd.Osaka, Japan	https://www.newcosmos-global.com/product/	KD-12B
371	New Cosmos Electric Co. Ltd.Osaka, Japan	https://www.newcosmos-global.com/product/	KD-12C

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	22.10.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	22.10.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	22.10.2013	(Metal Oxide Semiconductor / MOS Tin dioxide)
U(1)	12.12.2013	(Metal Oxide Semiconductor / MOS Tin dioxide)
U(1)	17.10.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	17.10.2013	Thermal conductivity

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Power generation equipment	0 - 25000 ppm	
Power generation equipment	0 - 40000 ppm	
Specifically designed for safety applications in fuel cells and gas-burning power generators	0 - 20000 ppm	
Specifically designed for safety applications in fuel cells and gas-burning power generators	0 - 20000 ppm	
Gas detector head, industrial use	n/a	
Gas detector head, industrial use	n/a	

Type
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
372	New Cosmos Electric Co. Ltd.Osaka, Japan	https://www.newcosmos-global.com/product/	XP-3110
373	New Cosmos Electric Co. Ltd.Osaka, Japan	https://www.newcosmos-global.com/product/	XP-3118
374	New Cosmos Electric Co. Ltd.Osaka, Japan	https://www.newcosmos-global.com/product/	XP-3140
375	New Cosmos Electric Co. Ltd.Osaka, Japan	https://www.newcosmos-global.com/product/	XP-3160
377	New Cosmos Electric Co. Ltd.Osaka, Japan	https://www.newcosmos-global.com/product/	XP-702 II Z
378	New Cosmos Electric Co. Ltd.Osaka, Japa	https://www.newcosmos-global.com/product/	XP-703 D

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	17.10.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	17.10.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	17.10.2013	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	17.10.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	17.10.2013	Hot wire semiconductor
U(1)	17.10.2013	Hot wire semiconductor

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Monitoring a risk of explosion	0 - 100% LEL	
Compliance work, safety and environmental monitoring	0 - 100% LEL	
Inspecting the amount of gas remaining in tanks	0 - 100 vol.%	
Measuring toxic and combustible gases in the ppm range	0 - 5000 ppm 0 - 10000 ppm	
Detecting small gas leaks, detection of one or two types of gas simultaneously	10 ppm (min.)	
Gas leak and trace detection in semiconductor manufacturing	1.0 ppm (min.)	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
379	Nolek Norsborg, Sweden	https://www.nolek.com/	SniffIT X1
380	Nova Analytical Systems Niagara Falls, NY, USA	https://www.nova-gas.com/analyzers/hydrogen/	335 Series
381	Nova Analytical Systems Niagara Falls, NY, USA	https://www.nova-gas.com/analyzers/hydrogen/	340 Series
382	Nova Analytical Systems Niagara Falls, NY, USA	https://www.nova-gas.com/analyzers/hydrogen/	380 Series
383	Nova Analytical Systems Niagara Falls, NY, USA	https://www.nova-gas.com/analyzers/hydrogen/	430 Series
384	Nova Analytical Systems Niagara Falls, NY, USA	https://www.nova-gas.com/analyzers/hydrogen/	436 Series

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	26.09.2013	Sniff IT technology®
U(1)	22.10.2013	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	22.09.2014	Thermal conductivity

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Leak test in various application areas	1x10 ⁻⁶ mbar.l/s	
Analysis of hydrogen in a binary gas mixture in process gases such as H2 in air, H2 in N2, H2 in CO2, H2 in Ar, H2 in O2, etc.	0 - 100% H2 in a binary gas mixture	
Analysis of O2/H2 in exothermic furnace atmospheres for copper, brass, or steel annealing, neutral heating, sintering, glass metal beds, or oxide coating of steel.	0 - 25.0% O2, 0 - 40.0% H2 (Model 340) 0 - 2.0% and 0 - 25.0% O2, 0 - 40.0 % H2 (Model 340) 0 - 100 to 0 - 9999 ppm O2, 0 - 40% H2 (Model 340L)	
Gas analyzer for power generators: Analysis of atmosphere inside hydrogen-cooled power generator during purity and purge modes.	0 - 100% H2 in Air 0 - 100% H2 in CO2	
Continuous analysis of up to 100% hydrogen in process gas streams. Also recommended for: H2 cooled generators, electrolysis units, refinery gas, heat treating atmospheres, etc.	Any between 0 - 2.0% ad 0 - 100.0 % H2	
Power generation industry	0 - 100% H2 in Air 0 - 100% H2 in CO2	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
385	Nova Analytical Systems Niagara Falls, NY, USA	https://www.nova-gas.com/analyzers/hydrogen/	870 Series
386	Nova Analytical Systems Niagara Falls, NY, USA	https://www.nova-gas.com/analyzers/hydrogen/	970 Series
387	Nova Analytical Systems Niagara Falls, NY, USA	https://www.nova-gas.com/analyzers/hydrogen/	7200-5
389	Nova Analytical Systems Niagara Falls, NY, USA	https://www.nova-gas.com/analyzers/hydrogen/	7900P Series
390	Nova Analytical Systems Niagara Falls, NY, USA	https://www.nova-gas.com/analyzers/hydrogen/	7900 Series
391	NTM Sensors Lewis Center, OH, USA	https://ntmsensors.com/	NTM SenseH2®

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	22.10.2013	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	22.10.2013	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	12.12.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	22.10.2013	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	22.10.2013	Thermal conductivity
U(2)	22.10.2013	Other / New Chemi-resistive ceramic

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Steel-making and metals industries ; Monitoring of atmospheres associated with steel- making and metal working or other industrial processes.	0 - 5.0%, 0 - 50.0%, 0 - 100.0% H2	
Continuous monitoring of syngas and gasification atmospheres or other industrial processes.	0 - 5.0 %, 0 - 50.0 %, 0 - 100.0 % H2	
Continuous analysis of flue gas for different combinations and ranges of gases including combustible gases	0 - 2 %, 0 - 5 %, 0 - 10 % Combustibles	
Monitoring heat treating atmosphere or process gases.	0 - 2.0 %, 0 - 50.0 % H2	
Industrial processes including heat treating atmospheres	0 - 2.0%, 0 - 50.0% H2	
Hydrogen fuelled back-up power systems, battery based UPS or cabinet system monitoring, hydrogen refuelling stations and hydrogen generation (electrolyzer) systems, fuel cell power devices including forklift trucks, any hydrogen monitoring requiring hig	0.25 - 4.0% (in air)	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
395	Teledyne Gas and flame detection (Oldham Arras, France)	https://www.teledynegasandflamedetection.com/de	iTrans
396	Teledyne Gas and flame detection (Oldham Arras, France)	https://www.teledynegasandflamedetection.com/de	iTrans 2
397	Teledyne Gas and flame detection (Oldham Arras, France)	https://www.teledynegasandflamedetection.com/de	OLC 10
398	Teledyne Gas and flame detection (Oldham Arras, France)	https://www.teledynegasandflamedetection.com/de	OLC 20
399	Teledyne Gas and flame detection (Oldham Arras, France)	https://www.teledynegasandflamedetection.com/de	OLC 50
401	Teledyne Gas and flame detection (Oldham Arras, France)	https://www.teledynegasandflamedetection.com/de	OLCT 60

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	07.11.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	07.11.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	07.11.2013	Catalytic Pellistor
U(1)	29.11.2013	Electrochemical Thermal conductivity Catharometer
U(1)	07.11.2013	Electrochemical Thermal conductivity Catharometer
U(1)	07.11.2013	Electrochemical

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
one or two point detection	0 - 999 ppm (Hydrogen)	
Oil and Gas Industry, Offshore Drilling, Utilities and Power, Petrochemical Industry, Municipal Water and Waste Treatment, Food and Beverage Production	0 - 999 ppm (Hydrogen)	
Designed for the use in boiler rooms and parking garages	0 - 100% LEL	
Designed for indoor or outdoor facility monitoring	2000 ppm (electrochemical) 0 - 100 vol.% (catharometer)	
Designed for manufacturers, refineries and other industries	2000 ppm (electrochemical) 0 - 100 vol.% (catharometer)	
Gas detection	2000 ppm	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
402	Teledyne Gas and flame detection (Oldham Arras, France)	https://www.teledynegasandflamedetection.com/de	OLCT 80
403	Teledyne Gas and flame detection (Oldham Arras, France)	https://www.teledynegasandflamedetection.com/de	OLCT 100
404	Pronova GmbH Berlin, Germany	https://pronova.de/en/products/	MGA45
405	Pronova GmbH Berlin, German	https://pronova.de/en/products/	MGA22
406	Pronova GmbH Berlin, German	https://pronova.de/en/products/	ACS Sensor
407	RAE Systems Inc. San Jose,CA, USA(Now Honeywell)	https://sps.honeywell.com/us/en/products/safety/gas-and-flame-detection	RAEGuard LEL

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	07.11.2013	Electrochemical Thermal conductivity Catharometer
U(1)	07.11.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	22.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	22.10.2013	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	22.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	22.10.2013	Catalytic

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Gas detection	2000 ppm (electrochemical) 0 - 100 vol.% (catharometer)	
Steel mills, Petrochemical facilities, Chemical industry, Pharmaceutical industry, Food industry, Refrigeration industry, Water treatment	2000 ppm	
Emission monitoring, leakage monitoring; portable and fixed	50, 100, 300 ppm	
Leakage monitoring, petrochemical, monitoring of H2-containing gas mixtures; portable and fixed	1, 5, 10, 20, 30, 50, 80, 100 vol.% H2 in N2	
Gas detection, various gases	0 - 200 ppm (min.) 0 - 500 ppm (max.)	
Industries: refineries, oil production, chemical plants, industrial safety, power plants, steel mills	0 - 100% LEL (combustible gas)	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
408	RAE Systems Inc. San Jose,CA, USA(Now Honeywell)	https://sps.honeywell.com/us/en/products/safety/gas-and-flame-detection	ToxiRAE Pro LEL
409	Riken Keiki Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://product.rikenkeiki.co.jp/	GX-2003
410	Riken Keiki Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://product.rikenkeiki.co.jp/	GX-2009
411	Riken Keiki Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://product.rikenkeiki.co.jp/	GX-2012
412	Riken Keiki Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://product.rikenkeiki.co.jp/	GX-8000 LEL
413	Riken Keiki Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://product.rikenkeiki.co.jp/	GX-8000

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	22.10.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	13.12.2013	Catalytic Thermal conductivity

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
construction, foundries, oil and gas, ...	0 - 100% LEL (combustible gas)	
Gas detection & monitoring	0 - 100% LEL	
Confined spaces, Refineries/Petrochemical, Waste water treatment, Utilities, Chemical plants, Hazardous materials, Fire services, Mining, Pharmaceuticals	0 - 100% LEL	
Personal monitoring, Confined spaces, Refineries/ Petrochemical, Waste water treatment, Utilities, Chemical plants, Hazardous materials, Fire services, Mining	0 - 100% LEL	
Single gas monitoring	0 - 100% LEL (hydrogen in air)	
Confined spaces, Refineries/Petrochemical, Waste water treatment, Utilities, Chemical plants, Hazardous materials, Fire services, Mining, Pharmaceuticals, Fuel Cell Facilities	0 - 100% LEL (catalytic) 0 - 100 vol.% (TC)	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
415	Riken Keiki Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://product.rikenkeiki.co.jp/	GD-A8 series
416	Riken Keiki Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://product.rikenkeiki.co.jp/	GD-D8 series
417	Riken Keiki Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://product.rikenkeiki.co.jp/	GD-V77D
418	Riken Keiki Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://product.rikenkeiki.co.jp/	SD-1 GP
419	Riken Keiki Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://product.rikenkeiki.co.jp/	FI-21
420	Riken Keiki Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://product.rikenkeiki.co.jp/	FI-800

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	13.12.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	13.12.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	13.12.2013	(Semiconductor cell)
U(1)	13.12.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	13.12.2013	Optical Interferometric
U(1)	13.12.2013	Optical Interferometric

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Various industries, oil and gas, petrochemical, ships, iron steel, automobile, etc.	0 - 100% LEL	
Various industries, oil and gas, petrochemical, ships, iron steel, automobile, etc.	0 - 100% LEL	
Semiconductor processing gases	0 - 2000 ppm (Hydrogen)	
Measuring gas: Combustible gas in the presence of hydrogen Petroleum refining plant	0 - 100% LEL	
Gas purity measurement	0 - 100 vol.% (Hydrogen in Air, N2, CO2)	
Gas concentration in drying facilities, purity control of several gases, etc.	0 - 100 vol.% (Hydrogen)	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
421	Riken Keiki Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://product.rikenkeiki.co.jp/	GP-01
422	Riken Keiki Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://product.rikenkeiki.co.jp/	GP-88A
423	Riken Keiki Co. Ltd. Tokyo,Japan	https://product.rikenkeiki.co.jp/	GP-88AS
428	RKI Instruments Inc. Union City,CA, USA	https://www.rkiinstruments.com/	H2 Specific LEL 65-2450RK
429	RKI Instruments Inc. Union City,CA, USA(A Riken Keiki company)	https://www.rkiinstruments.com/	H2 Specific ppm 65-2440RK
430	RKI Instruments Inc. Union City,CA, USA(A Riken Keiki company)	https://www.rkiinstruments.com/	PS-2

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	13.12.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	13.12.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	13.12.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	16.10.2013	Catalytic coated with molecular sieve
U(1)	16.10.2013	Metal oxide semiconductor, with molecular sieve
U(1)	16.10.2013	Metal Oxide Semiconductor / MOS

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Hazardous material, Refineries/Petrochemical, Utilities, Mining, Water/Waste water treatment, Chemical Plants, Pharmaceuticals, Fire services	0 - 100% LEL	
Gas detection & monitoring	0 - 10% LEL (low) 0 - 100% LEL (high)	
Gas detection & monitoring	0 - 500 ppm (low) 0 - 5000 ppm (high)	
Semiconductor, power plants, fuel cell industry, R&D applications, gas plants	0 - 100% LEL	
Semiconductor, power plants, fuel cell industry, R&D applications, gas plants	0 - 2000 ppm	
Hydrogen detection in battery rooms / battery storage locations petrochemical plants, refineries, automotive, etc.	LEL / ppm (customised)	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
431	Scott Safety Monroe, NY, USA	https://www.3m.com/3M/en_US/fire-safety-and-first-responders-us/	Freedom 6000
433	SENKO Co. Ltd. Korea	https://www.senko.co.kr/web2019/main.php	Hydrogen Gas Sensor(P/N SS1178)
434	SENKO Co. Ltd. Korea	https://www.senko.co.kr/web2019/main.php	Portable Gas Detector (P/N SP2277)
435	Sensitron S.r.l. Cornaredo, Italy	https://www.sensitron.it/	SMART 3G-D2
436	Sensitron S.r.l. Cornaredo, Italy	https://www.sensitron.it/	SMART 3G-C2
437	Sensitron S.r.l. Cornaredo, Italy	https://www.sensitron.it/	SMART S-SS

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	23.10.2013	Electrochemical Catalytic
U(1)	23.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	23.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	24.10.2013	Catalytic Pellistor type
U(1)	24.10.2013	Catalytic Pellistor type
U(1)	24.10.2013	Catalytic Pellistor type

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Wide variety of industries: refineries, oil and gas production, gas storage and distribution facilities, etc.	Customised	
Portable & fixed gas detector, industrial safety (petrochemical, refining) waste water, sewage treatment plant, mine, etc.	0 - 1000 ppm	
Gas detection	0 - 500 ppm 0 - 1000 ppm	
Industrial safety, industrial applications with tougher industrial requirements	0-100 % LEL	
Industrial safety, industrial applications, high performance products	1-100 % LEL	
For toughest industrial requirements, monitoring of toxic and flammable gases in	0 -100 % LEL	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
438	Sensor Gaz Tychy, Poland	http://sensorgaz.com.pl/	EKP-1/N/H2
439	Sensor Gaz Tychy, Poland	http://sensorgaz.com.pl/	EKP-1/W/H2
440	Sensor Gaz Tychy, Poland	http://sensorgaz.com.pl/	EKP-1/NW/H2
441	Sensor Gaz Tychy, Poland	http://sensorgaz.com.pl/	PC-31xx
442	Sensor Gaz Tychy, Poland	http://sensorgaz.com.pl/	PC-32xx
443	Sensors Europe GmbH Erkrath, Germany	https://sensors-inc.com/	AGM 22

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	05.11.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	05.11.2013	Thermal Conductivity
U(2)	05.11.2013	Thermal conductivity

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Measurement of hydrogen concentration	1x10 ⁻⁶ mbar.l/s	
Measurement of hydrogen concentration	0 - 100 vol.% H2	
Measurement of hydrogen concentration	Two subranges: 0 - 100% LEL H2O - 100% vol.% H2	
Measurement of hydrogen concentration and most combustible gases and vapors	0 - 100% LEL CH4	
Measurement of hydrogen concentration and most combustible gases and vapors	0 - 100 vol% CH4	
Industrial applications, Gas Warning, Process Control, Gas Quality	0 - 5, 10, 50, 80, 100 vol.%	

Type
hydrogen sensing element
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
444	Sewerin (Hermann) GmbH Gütersloh,Germany	https://www.sewerin.com/index.php	Snooper mini
445	Sewerin (Hermann) GmbH Gütersloh,Germany	https://www.sewerin.com/index.php	EX-TEC PM 4
446	Sewerin (Hermann) GmbH Gütersloh,Germany	https://www.sewerin.com/index.php	EX-TEC GM 4
448	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	EC4-1000-H2
449	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ10 SB
450	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ1 B

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	05.11.2013	
U(1)	05.11.2013	(Semiconductor) (ppm) Catalyst (% LEL) Thermal Conductivity (vol.%)
U(1)	05.11.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	21.10.2013	Electrochemical
U(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Standard pellistor pair
U(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Standard pellistor pair

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Gas leak detection indoors; leaks in pipes, valves, and other industrial products	0 - 100 ppm, > 100 - 2000 ppm > 2000 - 10000 ppm (H2)	
Gas leak detection indoors;% LEL (warning), ppm (detecting), vol.% (measuring) sensors available. Instrument available for warning application, in all combinations of two applications and for all three applications	% LEL (warning): 0 - 4.4 vol.% ppm (detecting): 0 - 22000 ppmvol.% (measuring): 0 - 100 vol.%	
Pipe leak detection Environmental air monitoringMonitoring of cemical or biological processes	0 - 10000 ppm (H2)	
Industrial safety: Mining, oils & gas, confined space entry, indoor air quality, industrial area protection, leak detection	0 - 1000 ppm	
Combustable gas detector	0 - 100% LEL	
Combustable gas detector	10% max.methane concentration	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensing element
hydrogen sensing element

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
451	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ2
452	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ21T B
453	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ21T BJ
454	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ21T SB
455	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ22B
456	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ23B

①	Acc date	Technology
①(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Standard pellistor pair
①(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Poison-resitant pellistor pair
①(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Poison-resitant pellistor pair
①(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Poison-resitant pellistor pair
①(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Poison-resitant pellistor pair
①(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Poison-resitant pellistor pair
①(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Poison-resitant pellistor pair

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Combustable gas detector	5% max.methane concentration	
poison resistant detectors for general purpose applications, particularly for fixed point systems where the consideration of power consumption is not an overriding factor	100% LEL max.	
poison resistant detectors for general purpose applications, particularly for fixed point systems where the consideration of power consumption is not an overriding factor	100% LEL max.	
poison resistant detectors for general purpose applications, particularly for fixed point systems where the consideration of power consumption is not an overriding factor	100% LEL max.	
Combustable gas sensing element	0 - 100% LEL methane	
Combustable gas sensing element	0 - 100% LEL methane	

Type
hydrogen sensing element

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
457	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ23TB
458	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ24SB
459	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ25B
460	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ3
461	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ31MB
462	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ35MB

①	Acc date	Technology
①(1)	22.09.2014	Catalytic Poison-resitant pellistor pair
①(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Standard pellistor pair
①(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Poison-resitant pellistor pair
①(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Standard pellistor pair
①(1)	21.10.2013	Thermal conductivity Pellistor pair
①(1)	21.10.2013	Thermal conductivity Pellistor pair

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Combustable gas sensing element	0 - 100% LEL methane	
Combustable gas sensing element	0 - 100% LEL methane	
Combustable gas sensing element	0 - 100% LEL methane	
Combustable gas sensing element	0 - 100% LEL methane	
Combustable gas sensing element	0 - 100 vol.%	
Combustable gas sensing element	0 - 100 vol.%	

Type
hydrogen sensing element

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
463	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ41TSB
464	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ546M
466	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ546MR
467	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ547TS
468	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ548ZD
469	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ548ZD/W

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Poison-resitant pellistor pair
U(1)	21.10.2013	Thermal conductivity Pellistor pair
U(1)	21.10.2013	Thermal conductivity Pellistor pair
U(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Poison-resitant pellistor pair
U(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Poison-resitant pellistor pair
U(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Poison-resitant pellistor pair

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Combustable gas sensing element	Ammonia 0 - 10% LEL, 0 - 1.5 vol.%	
Ideally suited for use in portable instruments	vol.%	
Ideally suited for use in portable instruments	vol.%	
Ideally suited for use in portable instruments	LEL level	
Ideally suited for use in portable instruments	LEL level	
Optimised performance gas sensing head for mining type applications	0 - 100% LEL methane	

Type
hydrogen sensing element

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
470	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ549ZD
471	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ549ZD/W
472	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ5MB
473	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ61
474	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ621T/1
475	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ621T/3

①	Acc date	Technology
①(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Poison-resitant pellistor pair
①(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Poison-resitant pellistor pair
①(1)	21.10.2013	Thermal conductivity Pellistor pair
①(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Standard & poison-resitant pellistor pair
①(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Poison-resitant pellistor pair
①(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Poison-resitant pellistor pair

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Ideally suited for use in portable instruments	LEL level	
Optimised performance gas sensing head for mining type applications	0 - 100% LEL methane	
Gas sensing applications	0 - 100 vol.%	
Optimised for fixed gas sensing applications	0 - 100% LEL methane	
Optimised for fixed gas sensing applications	0 - 100% LEL methane	
Optimised for fixed gas sensing applications	0 - 100% LEL methane	

Type
hydrogen sensing element

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
476	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ631M/2
477	SGX Sensortech Chelmsford,UK	https://www.sgxsensortech.com/	VQ641TS/1
478	SIM GmbH Oberhausen, Germany	https://sim-gmbh.de/en/products.html	HS 2000 10 00
479	SIM GmbH Oberhausen, Germany	https://sim-gmbh.de/en/products.html	HS 1000 10 00
480	Solidsense GmbH Krailing, Germany (company does not exist now)	http://www.solidsense.de/	SEC H2 20000 4 SE 5 V
481	Solidsense GmbH Krailing, Germany	http://www.solidsense.de/	SEC H2 20000 4 S

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	21.10.2013	Thermal conductivity Pellistor pair
U(1)	21.10.2013	Catalytic Poison-resitant pellistor pair
U(1)	17.09.2014	Catalytic Pellistor
U(1)	17.09.2014	Catalytic Pellistor
U(1)	28.10.2013	Electrochemical Solid-state electrolyte amperometric
U(1)	28.10.2013	Electrochemical Solid-state electrolyte amperometric

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Optimised for fixed gas sensing applications	0 - 100 vol.%	
Optimised for fixed gas sensing applications	0 - 100% LEL methane	
Continuous detection of the hydrogen proportion of the GC oven air	0 - 25% LEL (0 - 1.0 vol.%) H2	
Continuous detection of the hydrogen proportion of the GC oven air	0 - 25% LEL (0 - 1.0 vol.%) H2	
Hydrogen detection	0 - 20000 ppm	
Hydrogen detection	0 - 20000 ppm	

Type
hydrogen sensing element
hydrogen sensing element
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
482	Solidsense GmbH Krailing, Germany	http://www.solidsense.de/	SEC H2 20000 Micro
483	Solidsense GmbH Krailing, Germany	http://www.solidsense.de/	SEC H2 20000 Micro +
485	Solidsense GmbH Krailing, Germany	http://www.solidsense.de/	SEC H2 20000 SS1
488	SynKera technologies (Now IDTechEx) USA	https://www.idtechex.com/en/timeline/synkera-technologies-inc-now-idt/c61275	P/N 703
489	SynKera technologies (Now IDTechEx) USA	https://www.idtechex.com/en/timeline/synkera-technologies-inc-now-idt/c61275	P/N 724
494	Teckso GmbH Neukirche-Vlyn, Germany	https://www.teckso.com/	DVLS3

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	28.10.2013	Electrochemical Solid-state electrolyte amperometric
U(1)	28.10.2013	Electrochemical Solid-state electrolyte amperometric
U(1)	28.10.2013	Electrochemical Solid-state electrolyte amperometric
U(1)	23.10.2013	Resistive Metal oxide semiconductor / MOS
U(1)	23.10.2013	Resistive Metal oxide semiconductor / MOS
U(1)	28.08.2014	Catalytic

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Hydrogen detection	0 - 20000 ppm	
Hydrogen detection	0 - 20000 ppm	
Hydrogen detection	0 - 20000 ppm	
Chemical sensing, security and defense, etc.	1000 ppm - 2% (low power operation LEL hydrogen detection) 50 - 1000 pm (hydrogen detection)	
Chemical sensing, security and defense, etc.	50-1000 ppm	
hydrogen leakage in GC	Customer specified	

Type
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
497	Teledyne Analytical instruments CA, USA	https://www.teledyne-e-ai.com/	2000XTC
498	Teledyne Analytical instruments CA, USA	https://www.teledyne-e-ai.com/	2010A / 2010B
499	Teledyne Analytical instruments CA, USA	https://www.teledyne-e-ai.com/	2020
501	Teledyne Analytical instruments CA, USA	https://www.teledyne-e-ai.com/	212R
502	Teledyne Analytical instruments CA, USA	https://www.teledyne-e-ai.com/	2750
505	Union instruments GmbH Karlsruhe	https://www.union-instruments.com/	SIRA 8000

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	23.10.2013	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	06.11.2013	n/a

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
H2 purity analysis; detection of H2, He, N2, Ar, CO2 or a number of other gases in binary or multi- component sample gas mixtures; Power plant, petrochemical plant, fuel cell development, Electrolysis, etc.	Customer specified	
Air separation, petrochemical and refinery, turbine generators, nuclear power generation, steel/heat treating: H2 purity monitoring and analysis	Three ranges, application dependent	
Air separation, petrochemical and refinery, turbine generators, nuclear power generation, steel/heat treating: H2 purity monitoring and analysis	Three ranges, application dependent	
Detection of specific impurity in a binary gas mixture, monitoring of one component in more complex mixtures; Trace analyzer Specific binary configuration: e.g. H2 in Ar, H2 in N2 or O2; Air separation plants, H2 and He purification plants, Synthetic gas	0 - 25 ppm H2 in Ar, N2 or O2	
Design for turbine generator applications, H2 in air measurement	0 - 100% H2 in CO2 0 - 100% Air in CO2 80 - 100% H2 in Air	
Analysis of gas composition	4000 ppm (H2)	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
506	TROTECHeinsberg, Germany	https://uk.trotec.com	XRS 9012
507	TROTECHeinsberg, Germany	https://uk.trotec.com/	LD 6000, LD 6000H2
508	Unitronic AG Düsseldorf, Germany	https://www.unitronic.de/	USM VGSA
509	Unitronic AG Düsseldorf, Germany	https://www.unitronic.de/	USM 5.1-400
517	UST Umweltsensortechnik GmbH Geschwenda, German	https://www.umweltsensortechnik.de/	H2-Semicon®- Sensor-System
521	Xensor Integration B.V. Delft,NL	https://xensor.nl/	XEN-5310 XEN-5230

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	02.10.2014	(Gas sensor)
U(1)	01.10.2014	sonic (acoustic)
U(1)	05.11.2013	Resistive Semiconducto
U(1)	05.11.2013	Resistive Semiconductor (SnO2)
U(1)	24.10.2013	Combination of Resistive Semiconductor (SnO2) & Thermal conductivity
U(2)	05.11.2013	Thermal conductivity

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
leak detection	10 ppm to 2 vol% H2	
leak detection, handheld device, also combination of acoustic and gas sensor available	10 ppm - 20000 ppm	
Detection of many different gases, e.g. hydrogen	n/a	
Gas detection & warning system	Switching value: > 200 ppm	
Leakage monitoring in fuel cell systems, monitoring and control of chemical processes, fixed and mobile gas leak detection	0 - 40000 ppm H2	
Leak detection, e.g. in fuel cells, filling stations	H2: - 0.8 ... + 4.0 vol.%	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
522	Xensor Integration B.V. Delft,N	https://xensor.nl/	XEN-TCG3880
523	Zhengzhou Winsen Electronic Technology Co. Ltd.Zhengzhou, China	https://www.winsen- sensor.com/	MQ-2
524	Zhengzhou Winsen Electronic Technology Co. Ltd.Zhengzhou, Chin	https://www.winsen- sensor.com/	MC114
525	Zhengzhou Winsen Electronic Technology Co. Ltd.Zhengzhou, Chin	https://www.winsen- sensor.com/	MC115
527	Zhengzhou Winsen Electronic Technology Co. Ltd.Zhengzhou, Chin	https://www.winsen- sensor.com/	MC116
528	Zhengzhou Winsen Electronic Technology Co. Ltd.Zhengzhou, Chin	https://www.winsen- sensor.com/	MC119

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	05.11.2013	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	16.10.2013	Resistive Semiconductor (SnO2)
U(1)	18.10.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	18.12.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	18.12.2013	Catalytic
U(1)	16.10.2013	Catalytic

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Gas type measurement: Measurement of thermal conductivity, Measurement of concentration of Helium, CO2, etc, in air, Measurement of binary gas-mixture composition	n/a	
Gas sensor for use in domestic gas leakage detector, portable gas detector, industrial combustible gas detector	300 - 10000 ppm	
Gas concentration detection in industrial applications, such as natural gas, LPG, etc. combustible gas, gasoline, Combustible gas leaking alarm or detectors; Gas concentration meter.	0 - 100% LEL	
Gas concentration detection in industrial applications, such as natural gas, LPG, etc. combustible gas, gasoline, Combustible gas leaking alarm or detectors; Gas concentration meter.	0 - 100% LEL	
Gas concentration detection in industrial applications, such as natural gas, LPG, etc. combustible gas, gasoline, Combustible gas leaking alarm or detectors; Gas concentration meter.	0 - 100% LEL	
Gas concentration detection in industrial applications, such as natural gas, LPG, etc. combustible gas, gasoline, Combustible gas leaking alarm or detectors; Gas concentration meter.	0 - 100% LEL	

Type
hydrogen sensor

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
529	Zirox GmbH Greifswald, Germany	https://www.zirox.de/de/zirox/	TCS
543	Analox Group	https://www.analoxgroup.com/products/dams	DAMS (Distributed Atmosphere Monitoring System)
544	Nissha FIS, Inc., Japan	http://www.fisinc.co.jp/	SB-19-00
545	Riken Keiki Co. Ltd. Tokyo, Japan	https://www.rikenkeiki.co.jp/english/	SD-3SP
546	Riken Keiki Co. Ltd. Tokyo, Japan	https://www.rikenkeiki.co.jp/english/	SD-3GH
547	Riken Keiki Co. Ltd. Tokyo, Japan	https://www.rikenkeiki.co.jp/english	GD-84D-EX

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	23.10.2013	Thermal conductivity
U(1)	24.05.2022	Catalytic Bead
U(1)	07.06.2022	Semiconductor
U(1)	23.06.2022	Hot Wire Type Semi-Conductor Method
U(1)	23.06.2022	Semiconductor type
U(1)	23.06.2022	New Ceramic catalytic Method, Semi-Conductor Method, Hot Wire Type Semi-Conductor Method, Potentiostatic Electrolysis Method

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Hydrogen concentration monitoring	0 - 100 vol.%	
submarine atmosphere monitoring system	H2 Module: 0 to 100% LEL (0 Vol-% to 4 Vol-%)	
gas leak detection	0 ppm to 2000 ppm	
Leakage detection	Depends on sensor specification	
Leakage detection	Depends on sensor specification	
Leakage detection	Depends on sensor specification	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
548	Riken Keiki Co. Ltd. Tokyo, Japan	https://www.rikenkei.co.jp/english	GD-K88Di
549	Riken Keiki Co. Ltd. Tokyo, Japan	https://www.rikenkei.co.jp/english	FI-900
550	Riken Keiki Co. Ltd. Tokyo, Japan	https://www.rikenkei.co.jp/english	GD-70D
551	Bernt Messtechnik GmbH	https://www.bernt-messtechnik.de/	FL3100H
552	WatchGas Detection	https://watchgas.com/	PDM H2
553	WatchGas Detection	https://watchgas.com/	PDM+ H2

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	23.06.2022	Electrochemical type
U(1)	23.06.2022	Interferometer Method
U(1)	23.06.2022	New Ceramic catalytic Method, Semi-Conductor Method, Hot Wire Type Semi-Conductor Method, Non-Dispersive Infrared Method, Potentiostatic Electrolysis Method, Membrane Type Galvanic Cell Method.
U(1)	27.06.2022	Ultraviolet/Infrared
U(1)	27.06.2022	Electrochemical Cell
U(1)	27.06.2022	Electrochemical Cel

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Leakage detection	Depends on sensor specification	
Leakage detection	Depends on sensor specification	
Leakage detection	0-2000ppm	
Flame detector	n/a	
Disposable single gas sensor	0-1000 ppm	
Sustainable single gas sensor	0-1000 ppm	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
554	Umweltsensortechnik, Geschwenda, Germany	https://www.umweltsensortechnik.de	GGs1430 T
555	Umweltsensortechnik, Geschwenda, Germany	https://www.umweltsensortechnik.de	GGs2000
556	Umweltsensortechnik, Geschwenda, Germany	https://www.umweltsensortechnik.de/	GGs6000
557	Umweltsensortechnik, Geschwenda, Germany	https://www.umweltsensortechnik.de/	tre34546
558	BERNT Messtechnik Düsseldorf, Germany	https://www.bernt-messtechnik.de/	LaserGas II SP
559	Teledyne FLIR	https://www.flir.de/	FLIR GF343

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	06.07.2022	Metal oxide semiconductor
U(1)	06.07.2022	Metal oxide semiconductor
U(1)	06.07.2022	Metal oxide semiconductor
U(1)	07.07.2022	Metal oxide semiconductor
U(1)	18.07.2022	TDLAS NIR Monitor
U(1)	24.11.2022	Optical Gas Imaging

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Leak detection of combustible gases	0-1000 ppm	
Sensor with higher Sensitivity to CO , H2 und C2H5OH	0-1000 ppm	
Sensor for the Detection of H2 , low sensitivity to CH4 , CO and Alcohol.	0-1000 ppm	
Detection of specific gas from a mixture	5- 5000 ppm	
Continuous In-situ gas analysis	0.1% vol	
Wide area monitoring	n/a	

Type
hydrogen sensing element
hydrogen sensing element
hydrogen sensing element
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
560	MSA DEUTSCHLAND GMBH, 12059 Berlin, Germany	https://de.msasafety.com/	OBSERVER-i
561	EC Sense GmbH	https://ecsense.com/	TB200B-ES1-H2-4%
562	Neoxid gruppe	https://www.neoxid-group.de/	NEO983A H2-Sensor
563	Dräger Safety AG & Co. KGaA Lübeck, Germany	https://www.draeger.com/de_de/Home	Dräger X-am 8000 XXS H2 HC
565	Dräger Safety AG & Co. KGaA Lübeck, Germany	https://www.draeger.com/de_de/Home	Dräger PEX 3000
567	MSA Deutschland GmbH, Berlin	https://de.msasafety.com/Station%C3%A4re-Gasmesstechnik-und-Flammdetektion/Gasmessger%C3%A4te/ULTIMA%C2%AE-X5000-	ULTIMA X5000

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	18.07.2022	Ultrasonic
U(1)	29.08.2022	Electrochemical Redox reaction/ Resistance measurement
U(1)	25.08.2022	Schottky Diode
U(1)	25.08.2022	Resistance measurement
U(1)	04.10.2022	-
U(2)	20.06.2023	Catalytic, electrochemical

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Ultrasonic Hydrogen Leak Detector	n/a	
Indoor-outdoor Hydrogen monitoring	0 – 4% vol	
Hydrogen leak detection	0 vol%- 5/10/100 vol%	
Hydrogen leak detection	0 vol% - 4%vol	
Detection of explosive gases and vapours	100% UEG	
Gas detection	0 Vol-% to 4 Vol-%	

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen sensor
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen sensing element

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
568	neoxid GmbH	https://www.neohysons.de/en/produkte-und-services/wasserstoffsensorsystem/hydrogen-sensor-system-neo973i	NEO974
569	neoxid GmbH	https://www.neoxid-group.de/	NEO983
570	neoxid GmbH	https://www.neoxid-group.de/	NEO986
571	Draeger AG	https://www.draeger.com/	Dräger Flame 1750 H2 (IR3)
572	Draeger AG	https://www.draeger.com/de_de/Home	Dräger Polytron 5100 EC
573	Draeger AG	https://www.draeger.com/de_de/Home	Dräger Polytron® 5200 CAT

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	14.08.2023	
U(1)	14.08.2023	
U(1)	14.08.2023	
U(1)	14.02.2024	Triple-IR-Sensor
U(1)	11.03.2024	Electrochemical
U(1)	11.03.2024	Catalytic

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Hydrogen leak detection	0-5 vol.-%	
Exhaust gas measurement	0-10 vol.-%	
Hydrogen leak detection	0-100 vol.-%	
Hydrogen flame detection	40 m distance	
Detection of toxic gases and oxygen.		
Detection of flammable gases and vapours		

Type
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
hydrogen detection apparatus
n/a

ID	Manufacturer City, Country	Manufacturer URL	Sensor Model
574	Draeger AG	https://www.draeger.com/de_de/Home	Dräger Polytron® 7000
575	Draeger AG	https://www.draeger.com/de_de/Home	Dräger Polytron® 8100 EC
576	Draeger AG	https://www.draeger.com/de_de/Home	Dräger Polytron® 8200 CAT
577	Draeger AG	https://www.draeger.com/de_de/Home	Dräger X-am® 2800
578	Senso Control® Parker Hannifin GmbH	https://www.parker.com/de/de/home.html	H2 Leakage Sensor SCHATC

U	Acc date	Technology
U(1)	11.03.2024	Electrochemical
U(1)	11.03.2024	Electrochemical
U(1)	11.03.2024	Catalytic
U(1)	11.03.2024	CatEx-Sensor
U(1)	11.02.2025	Thermal conductivity detector

Application	Detection Range (H2)	Notes
Detection of toxic gases and oxygen		
Detection of toxic gases and oxygen		
Detection of flammable gases and vapours		
Multi-gas detector		
H2 Leak detection	0-4 vol-%	

Type
hydrogen sensor